

Implication of Platelet Indices in Seropositive Dengue Patients in Tertiary Care Hospital in Uttara Kannada District

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Abstract:

Background: Thrombocytopenia is the most common laboratory finding in dengue fever with considerable morbidity and mortality. Platelet indices have been investigated as platelet activation marker and MPV can be used as independent predictor of bleeding.

Objectives: To assess the correlation of platelet indices with platelet count in seropositive dengue patients.

Methods: A retrospective study was done in Karwar Institute of Medical Sciences, Karwar for a period of 6 months from Jan 2024 to June 2024. Serologically confirmed dengue cases were included and platelet parameters for continuous 3 days from day of admission were noted.

Results: A total of 180 dengue seropositive samples were studied. Mean PDW, MPV, P-LCR and PCT across 5 groups of platelet count were compared and showed a significant difference with $p < 0.001$.

Conclusion: Platelet indices play a significant role in early predictive diagnosis. PDW, P-LCR, MPV had an inverse relation with platelet count and PCT was directly proportional to platelet count.

Keywords: Platelet indices, Dengue, Thrombocytopenia, PDW, MPV.

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Introduction

Dengue fever is one of the most common and dreaded arboviral mediated outbreaks in India with increased prevalence year after year with considerable morbidity and mortality. One of the most common laboratory finding in dengue is thrombocytopenia which can lead to bleeding manifestation. Platelet indices like MPV (Mean platelet volume), PDW (Platelet distribution width), P-LCR (Platelet large cell ratio) and PCT (Plateletcrit) have been investigated as prospective platelet activation marker [1] and mean platelet volume can be used as independent predictor of bleeding. High MPV indicates increased megakaryocytic activity and low MPV indicates marrow suppression. Correlation of platelet count and MPV can potentially predict outcome. [2] Platelets with increased size and number of pseudopodia differ in size affecting platelet distribution width which increases platelet activation. [1] So there is a need to study platelet profile and understand its importance so that adverse outcomes can be controlled with great extent.

Objectives

To study the correlation of platelet parameters like platelet count, MPV, PDW, PLCR and PCT in seropositive dengue patients.

Materials & Methods

The study was done retrospectively at Karwar Institute of Medical Sciences Karwar, Karnataka for a period of 6 months from Jan 2024 to June 2024. Serologically confirmed dengue cases either dengue specific NS1 antigen assay or IgM antibody detection were selected. Platelet parameters for continuous 3 days from day of admission were noted. The data of platelet parameters (Platelet count, MPV, PDW, PLCR & PCT) in seropositive dengue patient's cases were taken from XN 550 Sysmex and Erba H560 analyser 5 part analyzers by using venous blood sample. The data of platelet parameters was noted and mean of platelet count and platelet parameters for three days during hospital admission were calculated. The parameters were

correlated and analysed. This study was approved by Institutional Research and Ethical committee.

Inclusion Criteria: Platelet parameters (Platelet count, MPV, PCT, P-LCR) available on day 1,2,3 for serologically positive dengue patients were included irrespective of age and gender.

Exclusion Criteria: Thrombocytopenia due to other causes other than dengue and cases with incomplete data were excluded from study.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis is done by descriptive analysis with t test and Pearson’s correlation. The descriptive statistics were reported using mean with the standard deviation (SD). A p-value <0.05 was considered as statistically significant. Pearson ‘r’ correlation coefficient was used to find correlation between platelet count with various platelet indices.

Results

A total of 180 dengue specific NS1 antigen assay or IgM antibody detected patients were studied. The study participants were with minimum age of 4 years & maximum age of 80 years with mean ± SD of 37.8 ± 17.1 years. Platelet count was divided

into 5 groups on day 1 and was compared with age. Out of 180 cases, 60 (33.3%) were above 1.5 L/cumm, 42 (23.3%) were with 1-1.5L/cumm and 51000-1L/cumm respectively, 23(12.8%) with 21000-50000/cumm and 13(7.2%) with <20000/cumm. Seropositive dengue patient’s platelet count was significantly associated with their mean age. (Table-1).

Out of 180 dengue cases, 108 were males and 72 were females. The prevalence was more in males. Table-2 shows comparison of sex distribution on the basis of platelet count. Gender did not show any association with platelet count in our study. Table 3,4,5 shows comparison of platelet indices (MPV, PDW, P-LCR, PCT) with various levels of platelet counts on day 1,2 & was done. All the platelet parameters were statistically significant with various platelet count groups(p<0.05).

Pearson correlation coefficient r was calculated between each platelet parameter and platelet count. (Table-6). Platelet count showed significant weak negative correlation (Figure1,2,3) with PDW, MPV & PLCR on day 1, 2 & 3. plateletcrit it was strongly positive and significantly correlated with Platelet count on day 1, 2 & 3(Figure 4)

Table 1: Comparison of age among different platelet group of the study patients(N=180)

Study parameters	Platelet count (platelets/μL)					Total (180)	Chi-square	p-value
	Up to 20,000 (13)	21,000 – 50,000 (23)	51,000 – 1 lakh (42)	1 - 1.5 lakh (42)	> 1.5 lakh (60)			
Age (in years)	< 20	0	0	6	5	11	36.908	0.045*
	20 - 30	2	2	9	13	15		
	30 - 40	1	7	11	8	11		
	40 - 50	4	2	7	8	15		
	50 - 60	2	7	3	3	2		
	> 60	4	5	6	5	6		

Majority of patients were seen 20-30 years and minimum were seen 50-60 years age group.

Table 2: Comparison of sex among different platelet group of the study patients(N=180)

Gender	Platelet count					P value
	20,000	21,000 – 50,000	51,000 – 1 lakh	1 - 1.5 lakh	> 1.5 lakh	
Male(n=108)	11	13	27	27	30	0.162
Female(n=72)	2	10	15	15	30	
Total	13	23	42	42	60	

Table 3: Correlation of platelet parameters at different levels of platelet counts on day 1

Platelet count (platelets/μL)	PDW (fL)	MPV (fL)	PLCR (%)	PCT (%)
< 20,000 (13)	13.99 ± 2.18	10.83 ± 1.11	34.21 ± 6.81	0.026 ± 0.026
21,000 – 50,000 (23)	14.03 ± 2.94	11.36 ± 2.81	35.86 ± 7.22	0.049 ± 0.034
51,000 - 1 lakh (42)	15.57 ± 3.99	11.84 ± 1.51	38.95 ± 12.72	0.089 ± 0.024
1 - 1.5 lakh (42)	13.02 ± 2.08	10.91 ± 0.97	32.91 ± 7.81	0.134 ± 0.02
> 1.5 lakh (60)	11.66 ± 2.31	10.12 ± 1.03	27.0 ± 8.39	0.216 ± 0.058
Total (180)	13.36 ± 3.16	10.91 ± 1.61	32.82 ± 10.26	0.132 ± 0.077
p-value	< 0.001*	< 0.001*	< 0.001*	< 0.001*

*Significant, ANOVA was used to compare among platelet count groups.

Table 4: Correlation of platelet parameters at different levels of platelet counts on day 2

Platelet count (platelets/ μ L)	PDW (fL)	MPV (fL)	PLCR (%)	PCT (%)
< 20000 (7)	14.03 \pm 0.92	10.60 \pm 1.12	32.26 \pm 4.77	0.019 \pm 0.004
21000 – 50000 (32)	16.29 \pm 3.6	12.02 \pm 1.2	40.23 \pm 10.68	0.041 \pm 0.01
51000 - 1 lakh (48)	14.82 \pm 3.13	11.51 \pm 2.01	38.51 \pm 9.92	0.084 \pm 0.019
1 - 1.5 lakh (46)	13.38 \pm 2.69	11.04 \pm 1.05	33.38 \pm 8.71	0.132 \pm 0.017
> 1.5 lakh (47)	12.38 \pm 3.27	10.39 \pm 1.18	29.28 \pm 9.76	0.221 \pm 0.058
Total (180)	14.04 \pm 3.36	11.15 \pm 1.53	34.85 \pm 10.37	0.122 \pm 0.075
p-value	< 0.001*	< 0.001*	< 0.001*	< 0.001*

*Significant, ANOVA was used to compare among platelet count groups.

Table 5: Correlation of platelet parameters at different levels of platelet counts on day 3

Platelet count (platelets/ μ L)	PDW (fL)	MPV (fL)	PLCR (%)	PCT (%)
< 20000 (8)	14.84 \pm 2.11	11.21 \pm 1.23	35.73 \pm 8.45	0.018 \pm 0.007
21000 – 50000 (36)	15.37 \pm 3.22	11.72 \pm 1.49	38.08 \pm 7.51	0.044 \pm 0.039
51000 - 1 lakh (49)	15.49 \pm 3.35	11.61 \pm 1.99	39.30 \pm 9.29	0.097 \pm 0.07
1 - 1.5 lakh (45)	13.64 \pm 2.14	10.99 \pm 0.88	33.51 \pm 6.81	0.128 \pm 0.017
> 1.5 lakh (42)	12.06 \pm 2.15	10.36 \pm 0.95	28.83 \pm 8.06	0.215 \pm 0.066
Total (180)	14.17 \pm 3.05	11.17 \pm 1.49	35.01 \pm 8.93	0.118 \pm 0.081
p-value	< 0.001*	< 0.001*	< 0.001*	< 0.001*

*Significant, ANOVA was used to compare among platelet count groups.

Table 6: Correlation between platelet count and other platelet indices

Platelet Indices	Day 1 (180)		Day 2 (180)		Day 3 (180)	
	r	p-value	r	p-value	r	p-value
PDW	-0.414	< 0.001*	-0.416	< 0.001*	-0.421	< 0.001*
MPV	-0.362	< 0.001*	-0.377	< 0.001*	-0.316	< 0.001*
PLCR	-0.420	< 0.001*	-0.392	< 0.001*	-0.415	< 0.001*
PCT	0.957	< 0.001*	0.977	< 0.001*	0.946	< 0.001*

*Significant

Figure 1: Pearson's Correlation coefficient, $r = -0.414$ with $p < 0.001^*$ showing weak negative correlation with platelet count and PDW

Figure 2: Pearson's Correlation coefficient, $r = -0.362$ with $p < 0.001^*$ showing weak negative correlation with platelet count and MPV

Figure 3: Pearson's Correlation coefficient, $r = -0.420$ with $p < 0.001^*$ showing weak negative correlation with platelet count and PLCR

Figure 4: Pearson's Correlation coefficient, $r = -0.957$ with $p < 0.001^*$ showing very strong positive correlation with platelet count and PCT

Discussion

Dengue is a growing cause of international health concern. The geographical distribution of dengue infection has significantly increased in past few decades.[3] It has had multifactorial mechanisms leading to thrombocytopenia and platelet destruc-

tion varying from reactive immune response to decreased platelet production. Possible mechanism may be due to direct bone marrow suppression of thrombopoiesis modulation of an endothelial cell by dengue virus or destruction of platelets by antiNS1 antibodies directing against the virus cross reacting with platelets. (khatri et al, 2018; kantharaj

2018). [3,4] In our study thrombocytopenia was seen in 120 (67%) cases which corresponded to the study done by Anuradha et al [5] and Shekhar G et al. [6]

In our study, out of 180 cases, majority of patients were in the age group of 20-30 years and minimum in 50-60 years. 108 were males and 72 were females. The mean age was correlated with five groups of platelet count and was found statistically significant ($p < 0.045$). The gender did not show any statistical significance. Study done by Mangshetty R et al [7] have shown male preponderance. The study done by Paul et al [4] showed no statistical difference with platelet count and mean age and gender.

In present study, comparison between MPV, PDW, P-LCR and PCT with five groups of platelet count was done. It was found that MPV and PDW were found statistically significant in various platelet groups. Paul et al [4], Meena VK et al [8], Mukker P et al [9] studies showed statistical significance between MPV, PDW with five groups and three groups of platelets count, respectively.

P-LCR and PCT was also compared with various groups of platelet count and was found statistically significant in our study which was consistent with Sekhar G et al. [10] Meena VK et al [8] study also

showed statistical significance with mean PCT and platelet groups.

MPV can be used as a marker of platelet activation and production rate. Increase in MPV with thrombocytopenia represents peripheral destruction and increased megakaryocytic activity.[11] Low MPV indicates underproduction/bone marrow suppression. MPV is inversely related to platelet count. [9,11] In our study, pearson correlation coefficient was done between MPV and platelet count which showed weak negative correlation and was consistent with studies done by Mukker et al [9], Passi et al [11] and Nehara et al. [12]

PDW is a marker of variation in volume in the platelet size and is elevated in the presence of platelet anisocytosis. P-LCR is an indicator of circulating large platelets, used to monitor the platelet activity. PDW and P-LCR vary with increase in size and number of platelet pseudopodia. On comparing PDW, P-LCR with platelet count showed weak negative correlation in our study. This was in accordance with Mukker et al [4], Nehara HR et al [12] and Gogaram et al. [13]

PCT is the volume of platelet as percentage of the total blood volume. Reduction in platelet count and PCT signifies consumption of platelets.[6] Our study showed significant positive correlation with PCT and platelet count and was corresponded with studies done by Passi et al[11], Nehara HR et al[12], Gogaram et al [13]and Wayez et al. [14]

Conclusion

Platelet indices play a significant role in early predictive diagnosis. PDW, P-LCR, MPV had an inverse relation with platelet count and PCT was directly proportional to platelet count. Platelet indices can be used as probable indicator for dengue fever with warning signs. It is also a reliable marker to differentiate hyperdestructive thrombocytopenia from hypoproduative and abnormal pooling of platelet.

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